

ROBUST

CRISIS GOVERNANCE IN TURBULENT TIMES

Framework for studying hybridity during crises

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1. Introduction

Deliverable D4.1 intends to contribute towards the existing knowledge on crisis management through the lens of hybridity. By doing this, it aims to conceptualise and operationalise a key independent variable within the ROBUST project – hybridity. Together with inputs from WP3 and WP5, it will also feed into building an analytical framework for empirically studying robust crisis responses in WP6.

Over the last decade, the combination of turbulence and crises have become the ground shaping the policymaking and implementation processes as shown in the WP2 of the ROBUST project. Rather than operating in stable conditions, the public administrations face short-term and long-term shocks, which requires a shift towards preparation and flexibility. This has materialised with the COVID-19 pandemic that highlights the reality of the modern crises – global, lasting for long time, having disastrous. With the poignant framing of the start of the 2020s as *Annus Horribilis* (Boin et al. 2021b), the daily routines of individuals, organisations and society were thrown into a flux. From the shock of the initial pandemic, the compounded nature of the crisis was exhibited with several long-term effects in healthcare, welfare, and the economy. From enabling access to timely medical aid, to ensuring subsistence wage to low-income individuals working in impacted sectors to ensuring emergency loans to enterprises hampered by the crisis, public administrations have been under pressure from multiple directions to meet the expectations set upon them. This occurred whilst the public administrations faced dwindling resources and trust from citizens following decades of reforms (O’Flynn 2021).

With rising turbulence, creeping crises and limited resources, the foci of the debate regarding the ‘who’, ‘how’ and ‘what’ have seen a considerable shift. Public sector organizations must possess the capacity to be prepared for the shifting conditions intra-organisationally, within the policy field and within the wider society. With the variation in the type of problems faced, public sector organisations have had to adapt to a more problem-oriented stance to seek for solutions. Academic literature has provided several normative perspectives and responses for addressing it – either through vague calls for flexibility or more concrete constructs through the ability to bounce back through resilience or the ability to innovate through robustness – with the latter being the focus of the ROBUST project. However, whilst the problem-oriented perspective provides a normative compass towards goals through the increased response capacity, the underlying transition regarding the structure and processes still remains vague (Carstensen et al. 2022).

The existing crisis-related public administration literature has been growing consistently in the past decades, providing more insight into the composition of actors, design of structures, decision-making processes and implementation (e.g. Kuipers and Welsh 2017; Wolbers, et al. 2021). The need for adaptive and innovative solutions during crises drives the emergence of

hybrid forms of *governance* (mixing the ‘ideal types’ of hierarchical, market-based and network approaches), *democracy* (mixing representative, participatory/deliberative, and direct modes of democracy), and *law* (mixing substantive, framework, and reflexive forms of law). Whilst existing literature has highlighted some of the overlaps within the ideal types and between the ideal type typologies (e.g. Moynihan 2009), hybridity, which focuses on the dynamics between the different ideal types, has received limited attention. Existing studies tend to deal with ideal types separately and look less at the subsequent mixing and matching among those ideal types. As a result, the existing literature consistently highlights a variety of mono-paradigmatic strategies for different stages of a crisis, with conflicts or contradiction between them (Cristofoli et al. 2022; Wolbers et al. 2016). Whilst ideal-type typologies provide a straightforward theoretical lens for comprehending the shifts, they are less suited for understanding the endogenous and more subtle exogenous shifts that take place within systems as they shift over time from one configuration to another (Tenbenschel 2018). This theoretical approach provides only a superficial glance of the possible interactions that these different instruments may possess interacting with each other. The hybridity perspective is expected to contribute to existing literature as well as provide some insight regarding the robustness of responses that move beyond recommendations that are aligned to specific ideal-type preferences. While a few studies have attempted to expand the lens of hybridity towards specific crisis scenarios (e.g. Lee and Wong 2021), these remain limited to single case studies rather than addressing hybridity in governments’ crisis response in a more systematic and conceptual way.

Deliverable D4.1 aims to conceptualise and operationalise hybridity in crisis response from the inter-related perspectives of governance, democracy and law. By providing a state-of-the-art overview of the literature of various ideal type typologies through the lens of hybridity, the paper furthers the understanding of the interactions between the different mechanisms and instruments utilised during the formulation of a crisis response and its changes over time. The deliverable highlights both interactions *within* specific ideal type typologies and *between* ideal type typologies. This enables to move away from the predominant focus on singular ideal types. It also provides a more holistic perspective towards understanding hybridity and better comprehending the shifts signalled from the surrounding administrative structure and crisis environment.

Following the introductory section, which addresses the methodology, the concept of hybridity and the context of crisis, this paper is structured into 4 core sections. Parts 2 to 4 discuss the ideal type typologies of governance (part 2), democracy (part 3) and law (part 4) highlighting the role of a crisis from tasks and challenges it creates; the response to the ‘who’, ‘how’ and ‘what’ of a crisis response from within them. Part 5 further develops the concept of hybridity in mixing and matching between the ideal type typologies followed by the conclusion.

1.1. Methodology

The core challenge with focusing on hybridity in crisis management is connected with the terminological ambiguity regarding the concepts of *crisis* and *hybridity*, which hampers traditional methods for conducting literature reviews (see also Gjatelma et al. 2019; Wolbers et al. 2021). The number of different keywords utilised as well as their interchangeable use in existing literature creates specific challenges in producing valid results. The use of a wide variety of concepts is present in the hybridity literature due to its broad appeal to a number of different fields, resulting in multidisciplinary papers (see also section 1.2 defining hybridity). This increases the risk of excluding papers relevant for studying hybridity, as authors rely on very different keywords and conceptualisations that can be difficult to cover through a standard systematic approach (Torraco 2005). The interchangeable use of different concepts results in the considerable increase of irrelevant texts for a systematic study (see Meuleman 2019 and Jessop 2003 regarding the variation in the usage of term metagovernance that also includes hybridity). As a result, the review of every single article using a keyword connected to hybridity is infeasible. Due to the attractiveness of the keywords related to the concept of *hybridity* and the subsequent variety in its conceptualization, the paper has opted towards an integrative literature review instead of a standard systematic literature review (Snyder 2019). An integrative literature review aims to uncover the core narratives within existing literature and find avenues of (re)conceptualization based on the expanding knowledge base available (Torraco 2005). This differs from a more standard systematic review, as the method does not involve gathering all the articles on the topic, but combining different, but illustrative approaches for hybridity (Snyder 2019). This is achieved through a combination of various search strategies to ensure the validity of results through triangulation. This enables to avoid the issues of fragmentation from the wide variety of concepts and their interchangeable use, but still provides an in-depth overview of the topic.

To achieve this, the report will rely on key articles from the field of public administration and crisis management. Within these two fields, the report focuses on seed papers that address governance, democracy and law, and combine them with the perspective of hybridity. Seed papers represent foundational academic works in the field, which serve as a base of references for researchers. With their role as a common point of reference, it is possible to use them as the basis for snowballing to determine the state of the knowledge in the field. Seed papers are identified by looking at times cited in the key articles as well as searching for the references (Webster and Watson 2002). The initial seed papers were complemented by a database search in Web of Science and Scopus regarding the relevant substrands of literature in public administration and crisis management. The database search was based on the following keywords:

- Hybridity/Hybridisation;

- Policy modes/Policy styles;
- Metagovernance/governance of governance/Metagovernance of modes;
- Hybrid Governance modes/Governance forms/Governance mechanisms/Governance arrangements/Governance approach/Governance strategies/Governance styles/Governance decisions;
- Hybrid Democracy/Democratic innovation/Democratic hybrid
- Hybrid Law;

AND

- Crisis management/Emergency management/Disaster management
- Crisis response/Emergency response/Disaster response

Annex 1 sheds light on the most important concepts and keywords that were used in the literature search. Due to the broad appeal towards the concept of hybridity, the search remained focused on top journals in public administration and top journals from crisis management literature. On the basis of the key articles and relevant papers from the database search, the paper at hand will highlight the core ideas, dynamics and relationships with regards to hybridity. With the multiple possible interpretations of hybridity – especially the enhanced use of single ideal type vs the combination of multiple ideal types – the paper opts to employ the combination perspective to avoid terminological obfuscation. The combination of multiple ideal types can occur on two distinct levels – within single ideal type typology and between multiple ideal type typologies – with the intent of this paper to highlight both.

1.2. Defining hybridity

Hybridity is a very prominent term, finding use in a number of fields including biology, linguistics and cultural studies (Brandsen and Karre 2011). It has also found considerable application within public management literature, with a steady wave of publications since the 1980s and 1990s and a new wave since the new millennium (Koppenjan et al. 2019). Hybridity serves as a tool to describe situations that transcend the boundaries established through ideal types with an emphasis on configurations lying either between the ideal types or making up a combination of the different ideal types (Skelcher and Smith 2015). For public management literature it has offered a theoretical perspective for describing a broad number of configurations that are difficult to cover with a mono-paradigmatic lens originating from a single ideal type (Jessop 2016). Over time the hybridity literature has evolved to cover the dynamics between the conceptualisation of different ideal types – including governance, democracy and law (Menard 2004; Skelcher and Smith 2015; Sørensen and Torfing 2019).

The mixing and matching of ideal types has become necessary to offset the disadvantages of one type with the advantages of another type. Within these different substrands, hybridity has been studied a) from a variety of perspectives - from actor perspectives, underlying

norms, values, logics (Brandsen et al. 2005; Skelcher and Smith 2015; Hooge et al. 2022); and b) from a variety of levels – from intra-organisational to cross-organisational to system level (Koppenjan et al. 2019). Whilst preeminent focus has gone towards the analysis of hybridity within single organisations and cross-organisational partnerships, there is also an increasing amount of literature on the system level looking towards the dynamics between the different decision-making and implementation streams (Meuleman 2008; Gjeltema et al. 2019; Jessop 2016). This became increasingly popular within academic literature from the 1990s through the works of Bob Jessop (2003; 2011; 2016) and Jan Kooiman (2003). However, within crisis management literature, the hybridity perspective has remained peripheral with rare initiatives following the theoretical perspective after the variety of responses observed with the latest COVID-19 pandemic (see Lee and Wong 2021).

This paper makes use of the definition of hybridity by Brandsen and Karre (2011) and combines it with approaches by Meuleman (2019), and Sørensen and Torfing (2019) – by analysing hybridity through the use of multiple ideal types. Hybridity reflects an attempt to find common ground through specific mixtures (either in processes or products) that are combined through ideal types with seemingly contradicting or conflicting rationale (Brandsen and Karre 2011). Hybridity in the fields of governance, democracy and law reflects a configuration of coordinated decision-making and implementation through designing and managing sound combinations of ideal types to achieve the most suitable outcomes (Meuleman 2019; Sørensen and Torfing 2019).

A configuration can compose of single and multiple decision-making and implementation processes and structures that rely on a number of instruments based on the different ideal types (Tenbenschel 2018; Meuleman 2019). The instruments stakeholders use combine ideal types at different levels – combining different ideal types within a single ideal type (for example, combining prescriptive and reflexive law), and designing configurations with ideal types from different ideal type typologies (for example, the use of hierarchy and prescriptive law). A single policy tool can rely on multiple instruments from different ideal types (see Levi-Faur 2014 for how multiple instruments can be applied within single policy tools). For example, the promotion of vaccination certificates during COVID-19 pandemic simultaneously attempted to incentivise desired behaviour through improved access to public spaces and curtail undesired behaviour by restricting movement. This highlights how a singular tool makes simultaneous use of different ideal types that can over time complement, contradict and conflict with each other, which is reflected through the hybridity perspective. Whilst combinations within single ideal type typologies – for example, combination of hierarchy and network within governance literature (see Bardach 2017) or representative and deliberative democracy within democracy literature (see Sørensen and Torfing 2019) – have been covered in existing literature, the combinations across different ideal type typologies remain considerably underdeveloped. The chosen approach to hybridity for this particular deliverable is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Hybridity

The configurations themselves reflect a compromise and are prone towards failure, as the actors make decisions based on the advantages and trade-offs of specific ideal types in relation to the compatibility with solving the key problems and existing dominant rationales (Jessop 2003). Alongside the long-term and short-term shocks from the crises and surrounding turbulence, the included stakeholders (whether it be the citizen, the private partner or the public organisations themselves) have developed expectations regarding the instruments used (Maor and Howlett 2020). The instruments cover a number of elements relevant to the crisis response, including the stakeholder composition (the ‘who’), the manner in which cross-organisational interactions as well as government-to-citizen interactions are set up (the ‘how’), and the measures used for the crisis response (the ‘what’). The measures chosen differ due to a large number of elements – for example, from the antecedent conditions that prescribe initial strategies to actors (un)willing to adopt specific positions. The factors impacting the choice of instruments reflect the ruggedness present in environments, with crises proving an especially challenging context (Tenbensen 2018; Boin and Lodge 2016). Due to this, rather than striving towards the most optimal solution, configurations are designed with having in mind what works in a given context (Jessop 2003; Tenbensen 2018).

Whilst the ideal types most similar to operating ‘business as usual’ may formulate the initial response to crisis, over time they may become insufficient to handle the problems (Boin and

Lodge 2016; Boin et al. 2021a). With the inability to provide an adequate response and the amplifying conditions of a crisis, the actors start deviating away from existing instruments to find mixes that address the problems, yet meet the expectations of different stakeholders (Duymedijan and Rüling 2010; Jessop 2003). Rather than being a straightforward process, it enters into an already existing patchwork of instruments, with similar administrative structures devising different configurations during a crisis, like the COVID-19 pandemic (Christensen et al., 2022; Giuliani 2023). Also, whilst a single instrument may reflect the origins of specific ideal types (i.e. the use of expert committees for decision-making), its effectiveness may be impeded or even altered through instruments from other implementation streams (i.e. political level superseding or picking and choosing specific information streams within the expert committee) adhering to other ideal types. Whilst the meta-governor is prominent in literature for the design of configuration (Meuleman 2019), in practice the configuration is affected by multiple stakeholders prioritizing different instruments, that they perceive to be optimal, creating a complex environment, in which the different implementation streams with different ideal type instruments compete and complement each other (Jessop 2016). Also, instruments may be subject to constant shifts and deviate from initial intended rationale to alternative ideal types (Bardach 2017). This can appear in quite subtle ways, for example, with more solidarity-oriented calls for adherence transforming towards command-oriented guidelines over time. It can also result in shifting between a variety of ideal types within different ideal type typologies.

As a result, any crisis response results in a mix of different measures, which may be a compromise between the goals and resources of different stakeholders. This also highlights the complex nature of instruments that can complement and conflict with each other. The complementing effect can occur with one instrument originating from one ideal type making another instrument from another ideal type more effective (Hooge et al., 2022). However, the conflicts can result in the different instruments curtailing or completely nullifying each other (Bode and Firbank 2009).

1.3. The context of a crisis

In the past decades, the literature on crisis management has progressed dramatically, in terms of events and areas covered, accompanying world's evolution towards a state of turbulence, "where events, demands, and support interact and change in highly variable, inconsistent, unexpected or unpredictable ways" (Ansell and Trondal 2018: 1), and an emerging poly-crisis, when several simultaneous independent crises affect multiple policy domains (Zeitlin et al. 2019).

Turbulence covers situations, in which events, demands and support interact and change in highly variable, inconsistent, unexpected or unpredictable ways (Ansell et al. 2023).

Turbulence can be both endogenous (i.e. turbulent intra-organisational environments) and exogenous with several core challenges impacting public organizations – shifting parameters, intercurrency, temporal complexity (Ansell and Trondal 2018). Shifting parameters highlight the changes in resources and tools available for stakeholders and the changes (Boyne and Meier 2009). Intercurrency reflects shifts in the dynamics and relationships within a given policy process, with previously independent actors or arrangements becoming interdependent (Ansell and Trondal 2018). Finally, policy processes have been planned with a predetermined number of steps and an established flexibility (Boin and Lodge 2016). Due to a shift in environment, these processes may unexpectedly be regarded as more urgent and affect temporal complexity. Whilst turbulence does not independently result in failure of existing configurations, thus differentiating from crises, it does provide long-term pressure and subject configurations towards increased vulnerability. What makes turbulence challenging is that it tends to highlight the weaknesses and amplify the tensions from trade-offs present in the configurations (Ansell and Trondal 2018).

Despite lacking consensus on the definition of crisis, the literature has suggested a significant number of concepts and typologies. The first is the concept of *crisis* itself, for which we adopt the widely recognised Rosenthal and associates' definition: "when a community of people, an organization, town, or nation, perceives a serious threat to the basic structures or fundamental values and norms of their social system, which, under conditions of time pressure and uncertainty, demands critical decision-making (Rosenthal et al., 2001: 6)." As WP2 shows, crises have often been associated with specific events and short in duration. However, the variations in scale, territorial scope and duration can also lead to *slow-burning* crisis (t'Hart and Boin 2001). Contrary to a fast-burning crisis, which is an exceptional situation with a clear beginning and end, a slow-burning (or creeping) crisis has a long incubation time and it may keep simmering long after the 'hot phase' of the crisis is over. It does not have a clear beginning or ending. It can remain undefined for a long time; it can change meaning during its lifespan.

As highlighted in WP2, the growing challenge from the combination of crises and turbulence results in a new context for public administrations, where they are subjected to consistent short-term shocks and long-term pressures. The stakeholders are subjected to consistently shifting challenges that are unpredictable and unknown. In the context of increasing pressure from crises and turbulence, public sector organisations also face decreasing resources. This necessitates public leaders to be able to put out smaller and significant fires whilst fine-tuning the public sector to meet the expectations set upon them by the public.

Regardless of the nature, cause, scale, scope and length, crises need to be managed. Hence, crisis management is a public policy (Rosenthal et al. 1991) that includes a set of preparatory and response activities aimed at the containment of the threat and its consequences (Ansell and Boin 2019). The response has both an operational and a strategic dimension, the latter

being conceptualized in terms of orchestrating and facilitating a joint response to an urgent threat (Ansell and Boin 2019). This necessitates administrative structures to adjust the existing sub-systems to handle the both the tasks and challenges relevant for crisis management to meet the contexts they operate in (Nohrstedt et al. 2018). The strategic dimension includes a number of tasks that need to be addressed, as Table 1 summarizes.

Table 1. Crisis management tasks (based on Boin and t'Hart 2010)

<i>Tasks</i>	
<i>Sense-making</i>	Diagnosing confusing, contested and often fast-moving situations correctly (with limited and often contradicting information).
<i>Decision-making</i>	Making strategic policy judgments under conditions of time pressure, uncertainty and collective stress;
<i>Coordinating</i>	Forging effective communication and collaboration among pre-existing and ad hoc networks of public, private and sometimes international actors (Hilliard 2000);
<i>Meaning-making</i>	Providing persuasive public accounts of what is happening, why it is happening, what can be done about it, how and who is responsible for what ('t Hart and Tindall 2009);
<i>Circumscribing</i>	Scoping the nature and duration of crisis support that will be provided and determining principles for targeting and rationing such support among often ill-defined social and territorial 'victim' communities;
<i>Consolidating</i>	Switching government and society back from response mode to recovery and 'business as usual', yet doing so without a loss of attention and momentum in delivering long term services to those who are eligible;
<i>Account-giving</i>	Managing the process of expert, media, legislative and judicial inquiry and debate that tends to follow crises and disasters in such a way that responsibilities are clarified and accepted, destructive blame games are avoided and a degree of catharsis is achieved;
<i>Learning</i>	Making sure that the organisations and systems involved in crisis management engage in critical, non-defensive modes of self-scrutiny and draw evidence based and reflective lessons for their future performance rather than politics-driven and knee-jerk ones (cf. Birkland 1997; Stern 1997; Deverell 2010);
<i>Remembering</i>	Publicly acknowledging that many crises and disasters are traumatic experiences for victims, responders and the organisations and communities involved, and responsively accommodating their desires that the community should 'never forget' ('t Hart, Ullberg and Kofman-Bos 2005).

The management of a crisis and the fulfilment of tasks depends on the ability of the government and society as a whole to make use of the different sub-systems and rationales to shape decision-making and implementation – involving the use of governance, democracy as well as regulatory instruments. Public administrations have existing configurations designed towards providing tasks in the most cost-efficient manner resulting in limited flexibility for crisis responses (O'Flynn 2021). With the challenges from turbulence and crises – uncertainty, urgency, threat – existing routines become ill-fitted for the crisis response, necessitating actors to make new combinations with alternative routines to compensate for the vulnerability of existing configurations. This results in a search for new alternatives by

finding new ways of utilising actors, instruments, processes and resources. Hybridity has served as a tool to describe these situations that transcend the boundaries established through ideal types with an emphasis on configurations lying either between the ideal types or making up a combination of the different ideal types (Skelcher and Smith 2015). It therefore provides a suitable theoretical lens for comprehending, how different instruments, both complementing and conflicting, are able to co-exist and the dynamics between them. This enables to move beyond simplified mono-paradigmatic approaches that provide limited comprehension regarding the dynamics present within different configurations.

In order to possess a comprehensive overview of hybridity in a crisis context, it is necessary to highlight the different available perspectives for the analysis. The ability to respond to a crisis effectively is dependent on the different interconnected processes – from preparation to upcoming crises, to the ability to make sense of the initial chaos, to design a working decision-making process and to ensure an implementation process (Boin and Lodge 2016). The different available theoretical perspectives provide insight into these interconnected processes. The following sections distinguish between three modes of hybridity: first, hybrid forms of *governance* (mixing the ‘ideal types’ of hierarchical, market-based and network approaches); second, hybrid forms of *democracy* (mixing representative, participatory/deliberative, and direct modes of democracy); and third, hybridity in *law* (mixing substantive, framework, and reflexive forms of law). Each ideal type typology provides a specific lens with which to analyse the different processes of the crisis response. The governance literature focuses on the dimension of “how” of the crisis response. It provides an overview of the forms of coordination through the existent structures and relationship dynamics between actors in the execution of different plans and procedures. The democratic theories provide an overview of the “who” with regards to the decision-making process. Through the democratic theory perspective, it is possible to get insight into the process of inclusion and the decision-making dynamics through the enablers and constraints present from learning capacity to institutional memory. Whilst the legal perspective has been less studied from the hybridity lens, which this report also intends to do, it still has importance in addressing different elements including the “what”. The many applications of law include its role as an input, with it framing decision-making and implementation arenas, and as an output, which serves as a direct instrument for guiding behaviour. The three perspectives are strongly connected and their inclusion enables a holistic perspective for analysing the toolsets that stakeholders possess for a crisis response. The analytical framework conceptualization of the ideal type typologies and their connections are presented in Figure 1.

2. Governance hybridity in a crisis context

The crisis and turbulent environment necessitate shifts in governance to provide a crisis response (Koppenjan et al. 2019). It includes the ability to analyse the situation and coordinate the crisis response (Christensen and Lægreid 2020). This ability is affected by the existing governance structure – in the form of how relationships among economic and political, formal and informal institutions are able to adjust and adapt to the crises (Kruke and Morsut 2015). This relationship involves a number of interactions, including the socio-political interaction patterns between a number of stakeholders, including state authorities, civil society and private actors (Bogason 1996; Kooiman 2003; Krahnemann 2003; Sørensen and Torfing 2007) and supranational actors such as the EU (Marcussen and Torfing 2007). The interactions result in a variety of dynamics, including levels of division/consolidation of authority and the perceived position of a coordinating body (from single to delegated to shared coordinating) (Meuleman 2008; Provan and Kenis 2008; Bovaird 2007), consolidation and utilisation of resources (Bovaird and Loeffler 2012; Kuipers et al. 2022), built-in flexibility for deviating with standard procedures and written in *ad hoc* deviations (Boin and Lodge 2016; Meuleman 2008; Hooge et al. 2022).

This section aims to provide an overview of governance literature regarding the context of crises. The relevance of crises is highlighted by the variety of deficiencies public administrations faced with past crises, whether it be the inability to gather resources and coordinate response during the refugee crisis (Boersma et al. 2019) or the inability to make sense of the situation and communicate measures during the COVID-19 pandemic (Boin et al. 2021b). The insight from this deliverable will serve as the basis on which to see the role of governance ideal types in providing robustness in crisis contexts.

2.1. Governance ideal types

Adjusting and adapting governance to the needs of crisis response is possible through a variety of mechanisms and instruments. Over the years these mechanisms and instruments have been clustered together in different typologies. The trichotomy of hierarchy-market-network has remained one of the most prominent toolset for scholars (Bouckaert et al. 2010; Meuleman 2019). The use of hierarchy-market-network in governance literature has been developed towards two connected goals: a) to provide broad generalisations of specific public administration reform trends over the decades (Pollitt and Bouckaert 2011); and b) to provide a language of classification of governance modes (Bouckaert et al. 2010; Tenbensen 2018). Whilst the former provides an overview of how public administration has evolved and developed over the years, the latter has been used as a pragmatic tool to communicate the different structures studied and experienced. Each ideal type possesses a distinct underlying

logic and rationale enabling coordination between actors and encompasses distinct advantages and disadvantages for their usage. The use of the different ideal types is reflected in Table 2 below.

Table 2. Governance ideal types

<i>Ideal types</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Examples</i>
<i>Hierarchy</i>	Relies on legitimate authority, which involves the use of management and structural instruments to establish a more direct and hierarchical control to achieve goals.	<p>Strong adherence to a prescriptive perspective of contingency plans through prescriptive legislation and instructions</p> <p>Formalised positions of authority, i.e. through cabinet members responsible for the crisis response, chief scientist</p> <p>Emergency resource allocation to task forces and committees to issue orders</p> <p>Use of penalties for punitive purposes.</p> <p>Prioritising specific information sources over others – narrow perspectives from experts</p>
<i>Market</i>	The use of market-based utilizes instruments focused on incentivization towards specific outputs, and measurement of existing actions to foster spontaneous coordination through rationality.	<p>Procurement and contractual relations with private partners for provision of key infrastructure (i.e. ICT solutions, logistics).</p> <p>Inclusion of private partners for maintaining and providing services</p> <p>Use of incentives through subsidies, grants, taxes.</p> <p>Incorporating additional perspectives from pressure – i.e. economic perspectives from interest groups</p>
<i>Network</i>	The use of solidarity focuses on interdependency through process-related instruments that aim to provide the space for interactions, facilitating knowledge and values to improve learning and (joint) decision-making.	<p>Decentralised networks, composing of multiple actors from national, regional and local level.</p> <p>Use of inclusive arenas for initial pre-crisis planning and implementation post-crisis (workshops, forums, bottom-</p>

up hackathons, collaborations between volunteers and first level responders).

Creating shared motivation and sense of responsibility during pre-crisis training.

Calls for solidarity in following decisions. (adherence to national policies on sentiments of belonging and trust)

Prioritising more information sources through holistic perspectives – democratisation of expertise

In practice, most governance arrangements make use of the different ideal types in a variety of combinations complementing and conflicting with each other (Jessop 2016). Within crisis contexts, the choice of instruments shifts from most theoretically optimal to alternatives that are feasible considering the governance capacity and legitimacy (Christensen et al., 2016). The governance capacity revolves around the implementation capacity of choosing and implementing different instruments through capitalizing on advantages and mitigating the disadvantages (Boin and McConnell 2007; Therrien and Normandin 2020; Christensen and Lægreid 2020). In conjunction with the governance capacity, there are expectations from the citizens as well as stakeholders involved to design specific configurations that address issues surrounding the crisis response, including efficiency, accountability, support, expectations, and reputation. The established legitimacy of institutions affects the behaviour of citizens and impact the adherence towards chosen measures, with low legitimacy contexts reducing adherence towards measures (O’Flynn 2021). Furthermore, the choice of measures for the crisis response has an impact towards legitimacy of stakeholders, with perceived expectations of an effective response setting a benchmark (Pierre 2020).

The limitations in choosing alternatives and the advantages and disadvantages of the different ideal types have resulted in a core dilemma highlighted in crisis management literature – on the one hand, the need for leadership, authoritative decision-making and hierarchy command (Christensen et al. 2016) and, on the other hand, the need for collaboration and networks, as they flexible and adaptive frameworks for responding to unique situational demands (e.g. Comfort and Zhang 2020; Kapucu 2006; Moynihan 2009; Nohrstedt 2018). This has led to a variety of responses to the crisis management tasks and challenges from the governance ideal types during the different phases of crises.

2.2. Crisis response from a governance perspective

The existing governance and crisis management literature provides an overview of instruments from different ideal types for the crisis response. The literature highlights both instruments planned for crisis response and *ad hoc* measures to combat unpredicted events. Prior to the occurrence of a crisis, the existing administrative structures provide specific limitations as well as prescribe certain actions that can both impede and expedite the response to crisis (Pearson and Clair 1998; Braithwaite 2020). The instruments from the pre-crisis planning and preparation are connected with all of the different governance ideal types. One of the more prevalent crisis-response instruments during the pre-crisis period is contingency planning with relevant stakeholders mapping resources and capacities for sense-making, decision making and coordination (Boin and Lodge 2016). For instance, for the COVID-19 pandemic, several countries had anticipated a pandemic spread and prepared contingency plans for pandemics based on previous experiences with a variety of pharmaceutical and non-pharmaceutical instruments to contain and combat the spread (Räsänen et al. 2023; Boin et al. 2020). The contingency plans can vary in level of depth and prescriptiveness, encompassing very detailed scenarios as well as more generic events, which affect the sense-making, decision-making, coordinating and meaning making (ten Brinke et al. 2010; Alexander 2005; McConnell and Drennan 2006). This variation can lead to reliance on different coordinating logics, from hierarchy, market and network. The adherence to more detailed emergency plans tends to emphasise the use of hierarchy, whilst the flexibility in generic events enables a stronger market-based and/or network logic. The use of pre-crisis planning results in specific path dependencies, which limit the choice of alternatives towards instruments that are compatible with the existing instruments as well as affect the openness to deviate away from the configurations (Jessop 2003; McConnell and Drennan 2006). For instance, during the COVID-19 pandemic, the Sweden's approach was based on long-standing WHO guidelines, and reluctance to change strategy reflected the strength of existing configurations (Boin et al. 2020; Zahariadis et al. 2023).

Accompanying contingency plans is the design of emergency law (emergency law further elaborated in section 4.2) during the pre-crisis preparation. Through the formulation of emergency laws, the stakeholders agree upon the allocation of resources and tasks during the crisis response (McConnell and Drennan 2006). On the one hand, it can serve as a tool of consolidation and centralization, with prescriptive legislation providing specific agencies and task forces with resources and power to steer the response (Räsänen et al. 2023). Alternatively, the emergency laws can orient towards more inclusive and reflexive strategies, with coordinating agencies' roles reoriented to facilitate the participation of other actors. This can be achieved through the establishment participatory arenas (e.g. reliance on inclusive workshops and meetings) for the crisis response as well as shaping the perspective of coordinating agencies' to be more facilitative of including other actors during the pre-crisis planning (i.e. public forums for formulating contingency plans and emergency acts) (Therrien

and Normandin 2020; Larsson 2017). With *ex ante legislation*, the public actors can also shape the relations with private partners. This can involve the framework for the inclusion of private partners through contractual relations (Alexander 2005) or planning the allocation of emergency funds for recovery through incentives (Braithwaite 2020). The various forms of using *ex ante* legislation, preparation and predetermined role allocation can have an effect on the speed of implementation and also limit possible duplicating activities and responsibility issues (Hermansson 2016).

Once the crisis hits, instruments related to pre-crisis planning are used in combination with a number of *ad hoc* measures that adjust and adapt other existing instruments. The crisis response structure can adopt a variety of logics, with hierarchical, market and network instruments all providing distinct advantages. The instruments from the initial phases involve attempts to control the chaos from the crisis, provide clarity and a timely response (Cristofoli et al. 2022). Whilst this can be achieved through a variety of rationales, there is a considerable reliance on hierarchy. This is illustrated in emphasizing adherence to prescriptive emergency acts as well as adapting existing legislation to determine roles, procedures and command lines for coordinating a response (Wolbers et al. 2016). Public agencies receive temporary emergency power and resources to issue orders and coordinate a centralized response (Moorkamp et al. 2020). A prominent example during the COVID-19 pandemic is the use of positions of formal authority with responsible politicians leaning on the use of scientific knowledge (often formalized through position of chief scientist) for sense-making and decision-making or becoming the face (both practically and symbolically) of the crisis response (Boin and McConnell 2007; Therrien and Normandin 2020). In addition, hierarchical measures can involve prioritisation of one information stream over another through limiting information streams with less priority during sense-making (Ansell et al., 2010; Wolbers et al. 2016; Christensen et al. 2022). From the government-to-citizen dimension, the interactions can be shaped through prescriptive regulations, prohibiting certain behaviors and enforcing other behaviors, combined a number of punitive measures, from the use of penalties and sanctions in order to enforce the desired meaning-making process (Christensen et al., 2022). Despite being financial instruments, penalties and sanctions are hierarchical in rationale, as their purpose is to be constraining rather than enabling or incentivising (Levi-Faur 2014; Meuleman 2019).

A market-based approach is used to provide actors flexibility and autonomy whilst adjusting to specific goals and including additional competencies in the crisis response. The market-based instruments enable coordination of the societal response through various incentive systems, including tax exemptions, emergency loans, subsidies, rewards and other support measures for covering costs from adopting specific behaviour (Larsson 2017; Wolbers et al. 2016; Christensen and Læg Reid 2020; Levi-Faur 2014). Financial instruments can be both incentivising and constraining (Levi-Faur 2014). The market-based instruments could also be used to mobilize external expertise and competencies through contracting and outsourcing.

Market-based instruments can also possess a supporting role during the crisis response, operating in parallel with the other decision-making and implementation arenas (e.g. providing critical services, like ensuring logistics for basic goods for citizens during critical infrastructure failure) (Boin and McConnell 2007). This support can be seen through the dependence of key infrastructure that has been designed through contractual relations, e.g. ICT solutions, communication system, logistics (Larsson 2017). In conjunction with the pre-crisis preparedness, the private stakeholders can become key actors during the crisis response.

The network-based instruments may be utilized to provide broader comprehension within the cross-organizational networks and acceptance amongst the relevant actors. As a result, informal contacts, voluntary agreements and calls for solidarity can become key in devising and complementing the crisis response. Crisis response can include volunteers, who provide critical resources as well as alternative decision-making and implementation arenas that are more flexible than public agencies (Larruina et al. 2019). Such initiatives are often – but not always – initiated bottom-up (Boersma et al., 2019). Whilst more common for short-term shocks, crisis management literature highlights the role of front-line workers collaborating with volunteers to determine *ad hoc* responses in case of limited resources (Boin and McConnell 2007; Wolbers et al. 2016). During crisis response, the societal actors can coordinate roles in services provision, decision-making as well as the exchange of resources and knowledge (Wolbers et al. 2016). These actors can opt to deviate from established power positions in contingency plans and provide *ad hoc* crisis response units (Moorkamp et al. 2020). Furthermore, the government can utilize its capital it has with the citizen population to call for adherence to measures of varying levels, which is possible during the rally around the flag moments (O’Flynn 2021).

2.3. Governance hybridity

Within governance literature, hybridity has been a widely used approach, with a number of configurations consisting of different governance mechanisms (Meuleman 2008; Meuleman 2019; Braithwaite 2020; Jessop 2003). Within the different configurations for crisis response, the balance and dominance of the different governance ideal types has varied. This is largely dependent on the advantages and disadvantages exhibited by each of the ideal types:

- The advantages for the instruments relying on *hierarchy* in crisis response have advantages in providing clarity and transparency that can quicken decision-making (Meuleman 2008). The use of authority by stakeholders can limit the amount of time spent on bargaining and negotiation, expediting decision-making and implementation and providing an urgent response (Boin et al. 2021). However, the adherence to formalized measures can result in considerable rigidity as well as they may increase ‘red tape’, which can become visible, when facing crisis-induced uncertainty (Entwistle

et al., 2007). Furthermore, the preference to the perspectives of a few actors may lead to underestimating the complexity and unpredictability in crisis situations and may fail to mobilize sufficient societal support (Kersbergen and Van Waarden 2004).

- *Market-based* instruments provide actors flexibility and discretion to determine the best alternatives to achieve specific goals, which can bring along major change without feeling enforced (Braithwaite 2020; Sax 2014). Furthermore, the measures can incorporate new competencies that can provide invaluable insight in complex situations and provide competitiveness between different alternatives (Howlett and Ramesh 2014). They might lead to more cost-awareness and efficiency. However, reliance on market-based mechanisms may bring market failure (Wu et al. 2015). Actors may lose control over the process and incentives may become subject to manipulation (Entwistle et al. 2007). Furthermore, reliance on market mechanisms, outsourcing and performance-related incentives may lead to a loss of control and transparency (Dommett and Flinders 2015).
- *Network-based* instruments expand available perspectives and provide more information for decision-making and implementation through broader inclusion (Peters et al. 2022). Furthermore, the inclusion of stakeholders and implementation of communicative tools can increase acceptance towards the results, trust and voluntary collaboration and compliance (Hendriks 2022). However, the reliance on deliberations and dialogue can lead to high interaction costs, lead to indecisiveness during urgent issues (Howlett and Ramesh 2014). In addition, deliberations may narrow the perspective of actors through group-thinking. It also might lead to unclear roles and responsibilities hence increasing risks for all parties and potentially blurring accountability (Hermannson 2016). Lastly, the reliance on solidarity for government-to-citizen relations may result in perceptions of inaction from the public resulting in loss of legitimacy (Pierre 2020).

Whilst literature has highlighted the suitability of single ideal types for distinct contexts (see Meuleman 2019, Howlett and Ramesh 2014), this perspective has limitations due to the volatility of the modern environments and the shifts within the priorities of relevant stakeholders. Overreliance on the single ideal types results in the amplification of the tensions to the point, where the configuration is required to look for alternative instruments. The endogenous and exogenous signals lead to constant shifts within the configurations from adapting, discarding and adopting different instruments (Tenbensen 2018). This is especially accentuated during the crisis context – from the pressure to respond quickly and the uncertainty regarding the problem – requiring the governance structure to have the flexibility to adjust and adapt for the different dimensions of the crisis (Ansell and Trondal 2018). With the limitations of the individual ideal types and the volatility of the current environment, the need for hybridity becomes clear.

The advantages from governance hybridity are also exhibited through the capacity to compensate for the disadvantages of one ideal type with the use of the other ideal type (Elst and Rynck 2013; Tenbenschel 2018). Whilst the idiosyncrasies of the different public administrations bring along differing dynamics, existing literature has highlighted some of the benefits from the synergies between the ideal types. The limitations within hierarchy regarding the rigidity of red tape and underestimation of complexity can be mitigated through a combination of market-based and network measures (Bode and Firbank 2009). Network measures enable to incorporate additional perspective to be able to comprehend and possess familiarity of the different viewpoints for the sense-making, meaning-making and decision-making (Moynihan 2008). Market-based measures provide access to additional interaction dynamics that can provide flexibility together with the formal measures from hierarchy (Levi-Faur 2014). The limitations of market-based measures with the loss of transparency, control and manipulation can be compensated through the use of hierarchy and network-based measures. The reliance on trust from the inclusion from network-based measures facilitates a level of goodwill for the increase of internal legitimacy to offset a lack of transparency (Elst and de Rynck 2013). The use of hierarchy provides a framework within which to limit market manipulation by market-based incentives as well as steer towards more specific goals (Braithwaite 2020). Network-based measures suffer from limitations in unclear roles and responsibilities, indecisiveness, and perceptions of inaction. The use of hierarchy provides decisiveness and a perception of a strong response together with clarity in role allocation and responsibilities (Elst and de Rynck 2013; Pierre 2020). Market-based measures can address indecisiveness by shaping behaviour through a set of incentives that have been designed to steer towards specific goals (Levi-Faur 2014).

Hybridity in governance changes consistently, as the different ideal types and their measures interact, complement and conflict with each other. . For example, hierarchical measures in the form of commands and rules can complement network-based measures, network-based measures can substitute the hierarchical measures with limited impact, market-based measures can provide new competencies for existing hierarchical and network measures that fail to bring in all the relevant perspectives (Qvist 2017; Braithwaite 2020; Meuleman 2019). The existing governance literature on crisis response highlights prominently the combinations of hierarchy and network instruments (see Moynihan 2009). The recent literature on the COVID-19 pandemic response also highlighted the variations of the combination of hierarchical and network measures. This was reflected in the use of both hierarchical and network instruments for cross-organisational as well as government-to-citizen coordination. For cross-organisational coordination, there was adherence to top-down policy guidelines and prescriptive regulation (Maor and Howlett 2020; Boin et al., 2021). With the legitimacy of top-down political support and emergency acts, task forces and emergency committees reflected both hierarchical and network measures based on the inclusiveness of different actors with both open and closed arenas highlighted (Christensen et al. 2022). The use of experts became an indication of the balancing act between hierarchy and network with the

role given for them – whether they were used to legitimize the top-down political level decisions characteristic of hierarchy or whether they were used as participants within the decision-making process more characteristic of networks (Christensen et al. 2022). Although less reflected in studies regarding the COVID-19 pandemic, the refugee crisis involved a considerable use of volunteers, who self-organised following the limited response by public agencies (Boersma et al., 2019). This reflects how parallel decision-making and implementation arenas can appear within configuration that adhere to different rationales. Whilst market-based measures have been less reflected during the COVID-19 pandemic in cross-organisational dynamics, its role was present through relations between the public and private partners within the cross-organisational dimension (e.g. the use of single private partners or collectives through associations) (Christensen and Læg Reid 2020).

With government-to-citizen coordination during the COVID-19 pandemic, the use of different measures highlighted the use of hybridity. There was considerable reliance on the use of punitive and prohibitive measures that curtailed behaviour with limiting movement by closing down public venues and mandating the precautionary non-pharmaceutical interventions (O’Flynn 2021; Christensen et al. 2022). However, this was accompanied with calls for solidarity, with the messaging accompanied by calls for consideration and care for the disadvantaged societal subgroups, examples of model citizens and politicians as paragons (Pierre 2020; Zahariadis et al. 2023). Also, the market instruments were highlighted with the use of incentives to steer the behaviour of citizens, by altering the attractiveness of certain activities with the use of tax breaks, subsidies and grants (Christensen and Læg Reid 2020). The different interconnected messages for citizens from the instruments – *don’t do this, become a good example, you want do this* – are conflicting, complementing, contradicting and a highlight of the combinations of the different governance ideal types and their interactions.

To sum up, hybridity in governance reflects how the interactions between hierarchy, market and network and between the configurations composing of the ideal types take place. Rather than clear differentiations, the instruments are interconnected with each other and shifts in contexts bring along both subtle smaller changes and fundamental changes that constantly adapt the configuration. It can appear in many forms – with literature highlighting the prominent combinations between hierarchy and network supplemented by market-based measures.

3. Hybridity in Democratic Crisis Management

In democratic regimes, the complexity of the challenges faced by contemporary governance demand a complex account of the ways in which citizens, who are subject to laws and policies, should participate in making them (Fung 2006). As major crises strike at the core of democracy, during these times, the challenges facing public administrations both increase and change, in terms of accountability, legitimacy, representation, and citizens' ability to get their demands met effectively (Afsahi et al. 2020; Boin and 't Hart 2010; Dahl and Tufte 1973). The urgency and efficiency of the crisis management demands democratic trade-offs, which then raise legitimacy questions. At least two types of crisis outcomes tend to conflict with democratic principles.

First, some policy measures to tackle crises may clash with fundamental rights, as in the case of austerity during the financial crisis (see e.g. Hayes 2017; Papadopoulos 2020; Salomon 2015), of movement restrictions during the COVID-19 pandemic (Spadaro 2020, Schmidt 2020) or the migrant crisis (Anagnostaras 2020; Grigonis 2016). Who decides on these issues must have the legal decision-making powers to do so, as well as the legitimacy and the social capital in the eyes of citizens. Authoritarian regimes were not only faster to restrict individual freedoms than democracies (Cheibub et al. 2020) but they also imposed more stringent mobility restrictions and contact tracing during COVID-19 pandemic (Frey et al., 2020). Likewise, authoritarian leaders in democracies with a high risk of democratic backsliding may capitalise on the state of emergency (Lührmann et al. 2020). In countries where the quality of democracy is higher in normal times, governments are more reluctant to adopt measures that are potentially in conflict with democratic principles (Engler et al. 2021).

Second, the crisis management tends to concentrate power on the executive at the expense of the legislative (Posner and Vermeule 2009), thus also raising issues of input and throughput legitimacy (Kickert and Randma-Liiv 2015; Schmidt 2020). In order to effectively handle crises, especially those that pose a threat to core values, it is crucial to employ prompt and adaptable executive measures, that simultaneously address immediate concerns and account for the inherent uncertainty in the evolution of the crisis and the unpredictability of effective crisis responses (Ansell and Trondal 2018: 46; Olsson 2009: 107). Such concentration of power in the core executive translates in its extensive law-making power and the adoption of a command-and-control structure through which the executive directs the public machinery (Thomas 2022). However, bold statements about leadership and power concentration may sometimes be undesirable and misleading, as leadership does not mean isolation and lack of consultation. As Boin et al. (2005) posit, top-down command and control may be a myth, whereas effective crisis management involves consultation, coordination and negotiated authority. Moreover, crisis management performance depends not only on governance capacity but also on governance legitimacy, in its input, throughput and output dimensions (Boin and 't Hart 2010).

On the other hand, executive dominance is frequently paired, reinforced and, at times, even replaced by expert know-how and technocratic rule. Lafont (2019) talks about an 'expertocratic shortcut' that undermines democracy. In her views, governments try to avoid the long and arduous road of inclusive will-formation and justification by asking citizens to just accept decisions by those who supposedly know better, i.e., the experts. Yet, such shortcut is harmful to democratic systems in two ways. First, by undermining democratic self-government, they tend to reinforce existing power relations. Second, expertocratic justifications and shortcuts to decision-making can validate reliance on individual opinion leaders and the purely instrumental use of evidence, thereby creating a resonance base for reactant, populist mobilization. Policies can be formulated by a limited group of 'experts' within a context of averseness to open and public debate (Zaki and Wayenberg, 2020).

Particularly in a long-term emergency with significant creeping crisis characteristics such as COVID-19 pandemic (Boin et al. 2021) questions about the crisis governance and democratic decision-making need to be made. In the context of Western democracies, it is fundamental to understand how political systems deal with the demands of the crisis management, how those dealings unfold over time and how that leads or not to democratically robust governance. Moreover, a prominence of the executive does not mean a total absence of other democratic institutions or the lack of space for citizens, individually, in groups or through representatives to make their voices heard in decision-making processes. Parliaments were never fully ignored or by-passed in the COVID-19 pandemic crisis (Bolleyer e Salát 2021; Chiru 2023; Engler et al. 2021) or during the financial crisis (Kickert and Randma-Liiv 2015; Maatsch 2015; Moury and De Giorgi 2015). On the other hand, some civil society networks and movements have played a crucial role in public sphere resilience by contesting measures, mobilising support and services and scrutinising government action (della Porta 2013, 2021).

3.1. Ideal types of democratic decision-making

In liberal democracies, representation is the core of citizen participation in the regime and the decision-making processes (Dahl 1966; Schumpeter 2013). Representative democracy is, thus, a type of democracy where elected people represent a group of people that voted for them, in contrast to direct democracy. It is dependent on periodic elections and voting, and is institutionally translated by parliaments. Political participation of citizens through voting has been considered by many as insufficient in terms of frequency and diversity of occasions to participate, and restrictive in the sense that it grants more decisional capacity to those that are more committed (della Porta 2013).

In recent years, alternative and complementary forms of democratic participation have caught the attention of both scholars and practitioners, as a way to overcome the crisis of representative democracy and promote citizens participation in policy formulations that

affect them. *The Oxford Handbook of Deliberative Democracy* (Bächtiger et al. 2018), the *Handbook of Democratic Innovation* (Elstub and Escobar 2019) *Mending Democracy: Democratic Repair in Disconnected Times* (Hendriks et al. 2020) or *Engaging Citizens in Policy-Making: e-Participation Practices in Europe* (Randma-Liiv and Lember 2022) are recent examples of collective volumes dedicated to new forms of citizen participation. Table 3 below provides an overview of ideal types in democratic decision-making.

Table 3. Ideal types of democratic decision-making

<i>Ideal types</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Mechanisms/Tools</i>
<i>Representative</i>	<p>A type of democracy where elected people represent a group of people that voted for them, in contrast to direct democracy.</p> <p>The advantage is representative legitimacy. The drawback is the distance from individual citizens who might not feel represented and the limited possibility for citizens to have direct influence in the democratic decision making (only by voting).</p>	Elections, Parliaments
<i>Deliberative</i>	<p>Discussion and debate among (and with) citizens [who] exchange arguments and consider different claims [and] can come to an agreement about what procedure, action, or policy will best produce the public good (Eagan n.d.).</p> <p>The advantage is that deliberation leads to group-based decisions enriched by individual opinions and originated from informed consent and compromise in this group of citizens. The disadvantage is that such deliberative arrangements often are not representative of the broader population, with over-representation of well-informed, higher-educated and politically interested citizens, creating differences in the possibilities to have democratic influence between groups of citizens. Moreover, deliberative arenas when they are disconnected from the bodies for representative democracy can provide for less transparent channels of democratic influence, without clear accountability arrangements.</p>	Mini-publics, citizens jury, citizen consultation, e-participation

Individual citizens decide to emit their opinion on issues [...] directly at the ballot box through universal and secret suffrage, even after representatives and governments are elected (Altman 2010: 7). Characteristic for this type of democracy is that democratic input given by individual citizens does not go through representatives but is aggregated into a direct democratic decision (or advice).

Direct

The advantage is that citizens can convey their opinion on substantive issues in a direct way into democratic decisions without the intermediate step of representation. The drawbacks are that this kind of decision making needs a lot of conditionalities to function well, like well-informed and politically interested citizens, large risks for misinformation and manipulation by different groups, a large turn-up in order for decisions to be representative of the larger population, and a sufficiently direct transposition of the citizens' aggregated decision into formal policies.

(preferably binding) referenda, plebiscites, petitions.

Several terms have been coined and sub-fields have been developed to make sense of the various forms of democratic involvement of citizens in the governance of the common good. Yet, there is still some conceptual blur, as terms such as participatory democracy, deliberative democracy and direct democracy frequently arise as synonyms, antonyms or overlapping among each other.

Coined by Joseph M. Bessette in 1980, deliberative democracy is, according to the *Encyclopaedia Britannica*, "a school of thought in political theory that claims that political decisions should be the product of fair and reasonable discussion and debate among citizens [who] exchange arguments and consider different claims [and] can come to an agreement about what procedure, action, or policy will best produce the public good. Deliberation has been considered (or confused with) a type of participatory democracy, it has been seen as a stream of it which has autonomized itself (Bohman 1998) as a different type of democracy. It has also been defined as the contrary of aggregated democracy (Knight and Johnson 1994). In other words, while representative and direct democracy models function as a pluralism market of the aggregation of individual choices of citizens, though voting or referenda, deliberation seeks consensus among the different positions. Reaching a consensus is usually the end goal, after a process that requires, not only voicing opinions or demands, but also interaction and exchange among participants – who often are different stakeholders, public and private (Pogrebinschi 2016). Based in communication and exchange between

participants, who are expected to give reasons for their political arguments and respond to others (Habermas 2006; Thompson 2008), deliberation may not simply be a form of decision-making, but also an opportunity for collective learning (Wagenaar 2003; Habermas 2006). Hence, as Öberg (2022: 180) defined it, “deliberative decision making is a problem-solving process based on competing validity claims, where actors justify their positions, listen to each other with mutual respect and are willing to re-evaluate their initial preferences in the light of counter-arguments and new informations”.

Direct democracy, on the other hand, is a form of decision-making in which citizens participate collectively on matters that affect them. The term is sometimes used interchangeably with participatory democracy (see, for instance, della Porta 2019) but it does not necessarily mean the same, especially in the broader context of representative democratic systems. In a direct democracy, citizens are directly responsible for making policy decisions, while, in a participatory democracy, citizens can influence policy decisions, but do not make them. Moreover, participatory democracy is aggregative of individual preferences, which are counted to form a majority, instead of to reach a consensus (Florida 2018: 37). Citizen participation can be binding or not for government, but politicians are still responsible for implementing those policy decisions. Some authors differentiate democracy/participatory from deliberative democracy in terms of procedure, with the former being a call for action and empowerment of individual citizens that requires less effort, but also less depth (thin engagement), and the latter being about communication, discussion and exchange of ideas (Manin 1987), thus requiring more effort and commitment (think engagement) from those who participate (Leighninger 2014).

3.2. Democracy during a crisis response

During crises, especially during long term ones, democracies face particular challenges. On the one hand, decisions have to be made quickly, which requires a strong degree of centralization and less time for debate, negotiation and accountability. On the other hand, precisely because difficult decisions are made and, frequently, fundamental rights are affected, the crisis management needs legitimacy and citizens acceptance, so measures are successfully implemented.

As mentioned above, the need for speedy decision-making during crisis may affect the functioning and role of democratic institutions and this is particularly true for parliaments. Parliaments traditionally have two main powers in political systems – law/policy-making and political control of the executive (Sieberer 2011). While these powers are still relevant during crisis periods, they may be exercised in a different way, as a democratic trade-off in the management of the crisis. The urgency to react quickly conflicts with the principles of separation of powers and rule of law (Zwitter 2012: 100). It is argued that the weakening of

the legislature in times of crisis such as the COVID-19 pandemic has paramount consequences for three reasons: firstly, legislative control over the acts and actions of emergency authorities is of vital importance for safeguarding the rule of law and democracy; secondly problems of input and throughput democracy gained major significance vis-à-vis law-making practices during the COVID-19 pandemic; and thirdly, emergency legislation adopted through fast-tracked procedures in response to urgent and compelling policy concerns is traditionally regarded as difficult to reconcile with requirements for good quality legislation (Griglio 2020).

The COVID-19 related literature has found that the role of parliaments changed significantly across countries and over time during the crisis, but their main task was more of scrutiny of governments' actions than of relevant policy-making (Bolleyer and Salát 2021; Engler et al. 2021). During crises, deviations from normal standards of policy-making are common in order to grant executives more efficient powers. During the COVID-19 pandemic, the involvement of parliaments in decision-making was narrowed in scope since many urgent governmental measures were adopted bypassing legislatures; and in their room for manoeuvre since their legislative prerogatives were reduced to little more than ratifying executive proposals (Griglio 2020). This reduction could vary across countries and type of political systems. The weakening of parliaments' role in law making was – overall – more pronounced among 'unified executives' than governments including major populist parties, pointing to a source of 'democratic vulnerability' in crisis situations (Bolleyer and Salát 2021). Furthermore, the prerogative to issue emergency regulations could affect the role of the parliament, with some states providing the mandate to the executive rather than the legislative power (Parrado and Galli 2021). However, crisis management requires legitimacy in the eyes of citizens, leading to the use of already established and introduction of new democratic instruments.

During the COVID pandemic, the adoption of new democratic instruments was exhibited by a number of citizen-led and state initiatives. The global crowdsourcing platform *Participedia* compiled a collection on deliberative public engagement processes that explore citizens' thoughts and values on trade-offs among health, privacy, and economic concerns related to the COVID-19 pandemic. The Open Government Partnership (OGP) also offered a snapshot of "Open Government Approaches to Tackling COVID-19" and drafted a Guide to Open Government and the CoronaVirus. The introduction of new decision-making and deliberation tools during the COVID-19 remained short-term practices, with initiative from both public authorities and volunteers, to maintain input and throughput legitimacy (Falanga 2020). In countries with well-established citizen engagement tools, either through direct or participative democracy instruments, the stakeholders would look to utilise them for crisis response.¹ In the United Kingdom, civil society organisations promoted proto deliberative

¹ See Foulkes, I. (28th November 2021), Covid: Swiss back government on Covid pass as cases surge, BBB News. Available at <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-europe-59380745>; Schminke, T.G. (19th September 2022), Liechtenstein's referendum on COVID-19 measures fails, Euractiv. Available at

democracy exercises to discuss on policy issues related to COVID-19, namely exit strategies and tracing apps. (Elstub et al. 2021). The introduction of new participation mechanisms alongside established decision-making tools leads to adjustment of existing and creation of new democratic hybrids.

3.3. The rise of democratic hybrids

Public decision making is often the result of the combination of several kinds of participation mechanisms, which come into play at different points during the decision-making process to complete political representation or expertise and not to replace them (Fung, 2006). Indeed, defenders of more citizens-centred democracy build on the idea that participation and deliberation must (at least) supplement representative and majoritarian institutions (Barber 1984; Fishkin 1997). Democratic hybrids are accentuated in crisis contexts, as the pressure to provide a quick response yet maintain the existing rights of citizens leads to adjustments towards hybridity in existing public decision-making.

In the past decades, scholarship on democracy has paid attention to democratic innovations (see, for instance, Schumpeter 2013) and their different typologies (see Table 4). In a scoping review of the scholarly publications on the topic, Elstub and Escobar (2019) highlight the scarcity of clear conceptual definitions and systematized typologies and try to clarify them. Hence, the authors advance with a working definition of democratic innovation - “processes or institutions that are new to a policy issue, policy role, or level of governance, and developed to reimagine and deepen the role of citizens in governance processes by increasing opportunities for participation, deliberation and influence” (Elstub and Escobar 2019: 11). With this definition in mind, Elstub and Escobar (2019, p. 28) mapped four conceptual families of democratic innovations – namely, minipublics, participatory budgeting, collaborative governance, and referenda and initiatives. They organized them, adapting the framework developed by Fung (2006). Hence, for the purpose of classification, the Elstub and Escobar (2019) use the following dimensions: i) which citizens participate and how they are selected; ii) the mode of participation and how the participants communicate with each other in the democratic innovation”; iii) the mode of decision-making, which can be assessed according to the intensity of work expected from participants and iv) “authority and power’, relating to the influence the participants have over what public authorities do (Elstub and Escobar 2019: 19-21).

Table 4. Democratic Innovations

<i>Democratic Innovation Family</i>	<i>Quasi-contingent features</i>				
	<i>Models</i>	<i>Participant selection method</i>	<i>Modes of participation</i>	<i>Modes of decision-making</i>	<i>Extent of power and authority</i>
<i>Mini-publics</i>	Mini publics, citizens assemblies, citizens jury, consensus conference,	Sortition	Discursive, expression, voting and listening	Deliberation and aggregation	Variable
<i>Participatory Budgeting</i>		Self-selection, election and purposive selection	Discursive, expression, voting and listening	Aggregation	Co-governance and direct authority
<i>Referenda and citizens-initiatives</i>	Referenda, Petitions	Self-selection	Voting	Aggregation	Advise and direct authority
<i>Collaborative governance</i>		Self-selection, and purposive selection	Discursive, expression and listening	Deliberation, bargaining and negotiation	Variable
<i>Digital participation</i>		Self-selection, sortition and purposive selection	Discursive, expression, voting, observation and listening		Variable

The mixing and matching of ideal types for democracy (representative, deliberative and direct) may be necessary, or at least desirable, to offset the disadvantages of one type with the advantages of another type. For instance, one type of democracy might enhance legitimacy, while other might function better to incorporate more technical elements. The mixing and matching of elements of the different dimensions of the various ideal types also generate ‘high levels of hybridity’, which is particularly true in the case of digital participation (Elstub and Escobar 2019: 27-8). A modern democracy can be home to models of pure types of democratic innovation that partly overlap and supplement each other leading to a hybrid of democratic models (Hendriks 2019). For instance, petitions organized by citizens may be presented in parliaments for MPs to discuss and decide on a given matter, hence matching participatory with representative democracy. A mini-public might mix discussion, exchange and learning in a typical deliberative mode of participation, but choose voting and aggregation of individual preferences as a mode of decision-making.

Mixing and matching of various features of democratic ideal types can also be found in different ‘sites’ and institutions, which are not necessarily restricted to lay citizens (Bächtiger

et al. 2018). Features of deliberative democracy can be found within formal institutions, such as executives, courts and legislatures (Quirk, Bendix, and Bächtiger 2018), as these may use majoritarian or consensual forms of decision-making. In courts, juries also provide a form of citizen deliberation in the judicial system (Bächtiger et al. 2018). Deliberative negotiation may also be found at the heart of cabinet or in public agencies (Steiner et al 2004; Sunstein 2017). Moreover, several countries have gone through 'governance-driven democratization', in which administrations consult with stakeholders or the broader public to reach better policies (Warren 2009; Randma-Liiv and Lember 2022). Outside formal institutions, civil society organizations have also adopted several practices and features of democratic models, mixing and matching them (Quirk, Bendix, and Bächtiger 2018). Over time, a large array of heterogeneous participatory practices and elements have been adopted by a wide variety of organizations and groups (Bherer and Breux 2012), including social movements (Della Porta 2013; Nez 2012; Polletta 2015); public administration organizations (Nabatchi 2010) or NGOs and community organizations (Eliasoph 2011).

4. Legal hybridity in managing a crisis

Crises that disrupt society and have a considerable impact on the democratic regime and fundamental rights, make crucial the role of law and regulatory instruments. Their importance is twofold. First, the crisis management needs to be effective and efficient, but it also must be framed within the boundaries of the rule of law. Second, legal instruments adopted to deal with the crisis are expected to deal with the uncertainty and volatility of the situation, which may be at odds with the essence of law itself, which is to be stable and offer predictability.

Rule of Law “refers to the ascendancy of law as such and of the institutions of the legal system in a system of governance. The Rule of Law comprises a number of principles of a formal and procedural character, addressing the way in which a community is governed. The formal principles concern the generality, clarity, publicity, stability, and prospectivity of the norms that govern a society. The procedural principles concern the processes by which these norms are administered, and the institutions—like courts and an independent judiciary that their administration requires.” (Waldron 2020). As disruptive events, crises also have an impact on the constitutional order and on the democratic functioning. Yet, to maintain the crisis management lawful, even if disruptive of normal times, countries usually adopt emergency laws, which are, in the majority of cases, constitutionally enshrined exceptions for exceptional times (Ginsburg and Versteeg 2020). Frequently these emergency laws grant more powers to the executive, in order to increase efficiency and efficacy (see, for instance, Carl Schmidt theory explained by Gross 1999).

4.1. Ideal types of legislation

Law holds different features and purposes and should not be understood as a monolithic instrument of governance. Laws and regulations are important policy outputs, as they are tools enacted by policymakers for altering the behavior of others according to defined standards and purposes, which may involve mechanisms of standard setting, information-gathering and behavior modification (Black 2002; Koop e Lodge 2017). In governance, law can be input or output. Law is input when it establishes the rules of the policy game, such as structure, authority, and process (Cosens et al. 2017; Torfing et al. 2012), i.e. it regulates the means through which collective goals are chosen, decisions are made, and actions are taken to achieve those goals (Rogers and Hall 2003; UNSTT 2012). Law is an output when it results from governance, it is the policy translated into law for implementation. Various types of legal instruments may be applied or designed (Table 5).

Table 5. Types of legal instruments

<i>Type of legislation/regulation</i>	<i>Description</i>
<i>Substantive legislation</i>	<p>Prescriptive legislation which governs how members of a society need to <u>behave</u>. It defines very clearly what the rules are concerning how stakeholders must act ((see Teubner 2006).</p> <p>While this kind of law creates certainty on how citizens should behave and facilitates the enforcement of the law by the authorities, substantive legislative may be easily outdated or unfit for situations that are unprecedented or that change frequently.</p>
<i>Framework legislation</i>	<p>Framework laws are laws that are more specific than constitutional provisions. They lay down general obligations and principles but leave to individual governing actors the task of enacting the further regulations or self-regulation and other specific measures, as may be required (Knuth & Vidar 2011). In other words, they are principle-based regulations that set the goals/outcomes, general obligations and broad principles to be achieved, but do not define or regulate the behaviour or actions which are desired or needed to achieve these goals or outcomes. Such legislation gives those subjected to legislation the discretion to determine themselves the behaviour needed to reach the prescribed goals/outcomes.</p> <p>Framework laws can also be implemented by higher levels of government, in order to leave to governing authorities at lower levels, the tasks of enacting further legislation and other specific actors as may be required, allowing for autonomy and potentially innovation. However, it may also create uncertainty on how to achieve those goals and how to comply. Moreover, actors need high levels of capacity to be handle the granted autonomy.</p>
<i>Reflexive legislation</i>	<p>Reflexive law is primarily procedural law. Instead of directly regulating behaviour to reach predetermined outcomes, reflexive law attempts to structure decision-making and communication processes with required procedures, for example, by regulating which actors need to consult each other or need to come to an agreement when making policy measures (see Teubner 2006). Reflexive law does not rely on static rules, e.g., fixed water allocations, when flexibility is needed.</p> <p>Because it defines procedures and not specific rules or goals, reflexive law is more adaptable to unforeseen situations, like those that may arise in a crisis. As it focuses on creating decision making arenas and processes, and potentially assigning involved actors, without specifying content, this kind of law demands different actors to deliberate and to collaborate, allowing more synergy in needs, ideas and information. It leaves more decision-making power and flexibility to those networks involved in the situations or who have expertise to decide on rules and solutions. However, it may also create uncertainty on what the rules are. Accountability is also harder to achieve given that law-makers delegate to others the regulation of behaviour.</p>

These typologies of laws may reflect different visions of how good governance should look like. Specific prescriptions, i.e., substantive laws, are often seen more consistent, reliable and less uncertain (see, for instance, Braithwaite 2002). Yet, others argue that ‘rules don’t work’, particularly in the context of complex environments (Baldwin 1990), which usually is the case of crisis. However, different types of laws do not necessarily need to be mutually exclusive. Cohen (cited by Baldwin 1990), for instance, claims that reflexive law paradigm can be used to supplement other forms of regulation, by articulating general, corrigible norms of norm selection, whose precise content will evolve over time in response to practical experience. The same can happen with framework laws, which set the more general goals and can be supplemented by more sectorial substantive legislation or put in practice by reflexive law. Simultaneously, framework laws help guide the implementation of the other two legal types. In this sense, she contends that reflexive law is not just a new paradigm of regulation but also a ‘metaparadigm’ for selecting among forms of regulation. This dimension of combination and flexibility has also been addressed by the interdisciplinary environment and sustainability literature, which has introduced another useful concept – adaptative law. According to this scholarship, the volatility and unpredictability of climate change forces governance systems, including legal instruments, to become resilient and flexible (DeCaro et al. 2017). In other words, adaptative law aims at developing structures, methods, and processes that manage for resilience and adaptive capacity (Arnold e Gunderson 2013).

4.2. Legal Instruments during crisis

In many crises, including financial, migration and COVID-19 crisis, many EU countries and institutions adopted combinations of hard and soft law, as the former grants more legal stability and enforcement, but the latter has the advantage of being fast, flexible, easy to issue, and thus adapted to rapid evolutions and changes in policies, adapted to deal with crises such as the current pandemic (Stefan 2020; Tsourdi e Vavoula 2021). From the literature on the COVID-19 crisis, the legal instruments that governed crisis management can be placed into two levels: a ‘higher’ level, where issues of rule of law, constitutionality and emergency laws lie (Bolleyer e Salát 2021; DGPRS 2020); and a ‘lower’ level, where are regulatory instruments deriving from the policies adopted by decision-makers (the democratic dimension) through various governance models (Christensen et al. 2022).

In the context of crises, particularly creeping ones that evolve overtime and affect different sectors and domains of public life, it is indispensable to address another type of laws - the emergency laws. According to Arnold and Gunderson (2013), emergency laws can be distinguished between:

- formal emergency law: constitutional norms determining the procedures for initiation, execution and termination of the emergency powers; and
- material emergency law: *ad hoc* created norms on the basis of emergency powers granted by formal emergency law.

On what concerns the higher level, combining the typologies described in the previous section, it might be possible to consider that formal emergency laws match the definition of framework laws, because to be able to offer flexibility, the formal emergency law should not too much interfere with the material emergency law and limit itself to defining the general character of the emergency (Zwitter 2012:108). This perspective seems to be corroborated by Kouroutakis and Ranchordas (2015), who claim that emergencies require less burdensome procedures and, hence, a de-juridification of decision-making processes.

4.3. Hybridity in Law

An overview conducted by the European Parliament on the European Union Member States' normative response to the COVID-19 pandemic reveals that the majority of Member States (19) enacted either a constitutional state of emergency, or a statutory emergency regime, or both, establishing, or sometimes adapting, emergency mechanisms, while only eight countries resorted to either special or ordinary legislation (DGPRS 2020). Moreover, ten member states combined the activation of emergency laws in combination with other arrangements, the most extreme case being Portugal which made use of almost all the available tools from states of emergency provided for in the constitution, to statutory regimes and ordinary legislation (DGPRS 2020). The study also shows that constitutional states of emergency were not the sole arrangements but they were complemented by detailed legislation of either a constitutional or ordinary level, in order to regulate the transfer of powers, duration, safeguards and the limits of the state of emergency (DGPRS 2020).

At the 'lower' level, several regulatory instruments were adopted in various policy areas during COVID-19 pandemic. Many countries adopted policy approaches, operationalised through a 'regulatory mix' of social distancing measures, namely requirements and/or recommendations (Alemanno 2020). For instance, social distance measures, such as the prohibition of public gatherings or workplace and school closures, were combined with voluntary measures, such as personal protective measures (cough etiquette and/or facemasks); and environmental measures (routine cleaning of surfaces and ensuring appropriate ventilation) (Alemanno 2020).

Hybridity is also possible to occur over time, i.e., the combination and/or replacement of types of laws that govern the crisis management as the crisis unfolds and decision-makers gain new information and learn from experience. For instance, the Finnish government adopted a hybrid strategy, which moved "from extensive restrictive measures to enhanced management of the pandemic. Alongside the controlled dismantling of restrictive measures, the strategy focused on testing, tracing, isolating, and treating" (Tiirinki et al. 2020).

5. Hybridity through mixing and matching of ideal type typologies

Whilst the previous sections highlighted hybridity *within* the ideal type typologies, the existing literature also gives indications of certain mixes *between* the different typologies. Mixing and matching is encouraged through the compatibilities present between the different ideal types (Tenbensen 2018). This compatibility is exhibited through the supplementing and complementing effects by compensating for the disadvantages of the ideal types and capitalising on the advantages of the different ideal types (Hendriks 2022; Elst and Rynck 2013). These compatibilities experience shifts within the different contexts, including crisis situations, adjusting the suitable configurations for response regarding the ‘who’, ‘how’ and ‘what’ (Meuleman 2019). The shifts of the configurations are dependent on the altered expectations of the relevant stakeholders together with the changing conditions in policy-making and implementations regarding urgency and substance of the crisis (Maor and Howlett 2020; Ansell and Trondal 2018). Whilst existing literature has focused on single ideal type typologies, these conceptualisations have also included elements from the other ideal type typologies, thus providing insight into the possible combinations between the different ideal type typologies (see Figure 2).

Figure 2. Mixing and matching

5.1. Mixing of ideal type typologies in responding to crisis

Whilst the previous sections highlighted the ideal types within a single ideal type typology, configurations between the different ideal type typologies have also been demonstrated. The existing crisis management and public management literature has highlighted a number of hybrid configurations that use combinations of ideal types derived from governance, democracy and law. These insights have stemmed from the past decades through the previous creeping crises, including the COVID-19 pandemic, the migration crisis and the financial crisis (Boin et al. 2021; Boersma et al. 2019) as well as smaller, shorter and localised crises that were the result of natural disasters (Ten Brinke et al. 2010; Boin and Lodge 2016).

The first form of crisis response relies predominantly on *ex ante* instruments with the use of detailed scenario-based plans. The emergency plans are often constructed from specific scenarios, outlining both the substance of the crisis as well as the existing conditions for response (Ten Brinke et al. 2010). The differing context can affect the emphasis within the *ex ante* instruments utilised. With reliance on the detailed scenario-based emergency plans within a context of limited vertical and horizontal fragmentation, the configuration is oriented towards combining instruments from hierarchy, prescriptive legislation and executive dominance over representative democracy. When plans are highly detailed, they are often accompanied by supporting prescriptive regulation that outlines the obligations for stakeholders to contribute as well as prepare for specific situations (McConnell and Drennan 2006). With reliance on past experience and existing expertise, the decision-making and coordinating shifts away from the use of public forums towards more limited decision-making arenas. This is also reflected in the combination of governance mechanisms, with the use of command and control through the use of laws, policy guidelines, conventions and protocols (Boin and Lodge 2016; McConnell and Drennan 2006). With higher levels of vertical and horizontal fragmentation, the inability to concentrate the relevant resources and the interdependencies between stakeholders necessitate a larger diversity between actors. It involves similar emphasis to pre-crisis planning, but the lack of established asymmetries result in more interactions between relevant stakeholders to ensure resource provision (McConnell and Drennan 2006). The governance mechanisms will therefore vary between the use of hierarchical and network-based instruments to manage both government-to-citizen and cross-organisational relations. The use of hierarchical measures have a role in providing the urgency alongside a symbol of a strong response with network-based instruments ensuring the required resources (Pierre 2020; Zahariadis et al. 2023). The decision-making can start to vary with a structure reflecting polycentricity through multiple decision-making arenas at different levels.

Although crisis planning has been one of the core tenets in crisis management, the ability to plan and have suitable plans for every contingency is impossible (Wolbers et al. 2021; Ten Brinke et al., 2010). As a result, actors may have to rely on configurations with less pre-crisis

planning and more on an *ad hoc* combination of instruments (Capano and Toth 2023). From this originates a second form of crisis response, which relies on the self-organisation by public actors. With a lack or incompatibility of suitable *ex ante* instruments, relevant actors will adapt and adjust existing instruments to accommodate towards the new context, yet maintain compatibility with the initial goal. Such an approach can adopt a number of configurations with a prominent example being the use of hierarchy, market, representative democracy and framework legislation. With the pressure from the crisis, the initial reaction of stakeholders is towards centralisation and providing leadership figure (Boin et al. 2020). The inability to communicate a strong response may result in losing legitimacy amongst citizens even if the measures are designed with the 'business as usual' way of making decisions and implementation in mind (Pierre 2020; Zahariadis et al., 2023). As a result, actors interpret and adjust existing legislative documents and policy guidelines to create an *ad hoc* structure (Capano and Toth 2023). This can be achieved through emergency powers that are provided for limited number of actors to make *ad hoc* decisions and possess the relevant resources for a swift crisis response (Boin et al. 2021). In conjunction with the hierarchical tools, stakeholders attempt to make use of market-based instruments with the flexibility to readjust the relations with private partners (Braithwaite 2020). The intention is to aim towards compatibility with specific goals and then make use of available instruments to reach a specific result (Capano and Toth 2023). The formalisation of relevant structures, processes and instruments may happen *ex post* once the more acute crisis period has passed.

The third hybrid form of crisis response has been more prevalent in crises with a specific locality (especially in the case of natural disasters), as the use of trust-based instruments is contingent on social networks and common beliefs, which are prevalent in local communities (Wolbers et al. 2016; Boersma et al. 2019). This configuration relies on solidarity and commitment to each other, resulting in a bottom-up *ad hoc* configuration (Jessop 2016). This relies strongly on citizens and societal actors, with the use of informal and trust-based instruments preferred over established formal instruments (Boersma et al. 2019; Schmidt et al. 2018; Wolbers et al. 2016). This is likely to result in configurations of network, deliberative and reflexive instruments. The decision-making relies on a broad range of stakeholders, as public, private and societal actors (Wolbers et al. 2016). This leads to a polycentric structure with multiple connected decision-making and implementation streams. Due to the large volatility of emergent community responses, established instruments are used for ensuring coordination, often through the use of platforms, which affect the levels of inclusion (Schmidt et al., 2018). The hybrid form uses participative instruments due to their openness towards voluntarism (Boersma et al., 2019). Configurations within this type can adopt complementing or supplemental roles with more traditional policy-making and service provision, where citizen initiatives act in collaboration with other public and private organisations (Meijer 2011). Furthermore, with the failure of existing implementation streams, this hybrid form may start protesting and aim to reform the existing decision-making and service provision processes through direct instruments in the form of public petitions (Boersma et al., 2019).

Over time the emergent responses start to be formalised, and the formalisation may lead to the utilisation of hierarchy and adherence to prescriptive legal instruments for ensuring stability and legitimacy (Boersma et al., 2019). The formalisation aims to curtail unpredictability from trust-based instruments and improve control to establish a more stable position within the environment (Wolbers et al. 2016).

The different hybrid forms highlight examples of the possible synergies developed by mixing and matching instruments from the different ideal type typologies. An example of synergy is the use of hierarchy and substantive legislation provide complementing effects. Substantive legislation can provide a framing role as an input, where it facilitates the creation of hierarchical coordination with allocation of mandate and resources (Räisänen et al. 2023). Substantive legislation can also be used as an output tool to prescribe concrete actions for stakeholders to follow. Another example is the use of deliberative democracy and networks. The tools from the respective ideal types adhere to similar values with an emphasis on inclusion of stakeholders and plurality of perspectives (Hendriks 2022). This leads to possible overlaps with deliberative democracy and networks engaging societal actors and citizens from the start of the decision-making process to implementation as equal actors. These highlight only a number of instances, where the combination of measures from different ideal type typologies can lead to complementing effects leading to new possible practices and routines. Furthermore, it can serve as a base for engendering new values within the administrative structures (Ibid.).

5.2. Challenges and tensions related to hybridity

Creating configurations from different ideal types and ideal type typologies possess inherent tensions, conflicts and incoherence requiring a constant matching process to create compatible combinations (Tenbensen 2018). Due to the preminent focus on single ideal types, the conflicts existent in literature are mostly addressed at a theoretical level (Meuleman 2019; Bode and Firbank 2009). These tensions may originate from different sources – from limitations of the individual instrument to address the conditions of the crisis to the incompatibilities of the underlying logic of interacting with other instruments (Howlett and Ramesh 2014). The reliance on pre-crisis period for sense-making and decision-making through limited decision-making arenas, and hierarchical implementation creates inflexibilities in being able to adjust to scenarios beyond the plan. The inability to deviate from a prescriptive plan creates notions of a false sense of control, limiting both timely and compatible responses (Ten Brinke et al. 2010). Furthermore, limiting the participation to a few key actors diminishes the information streams available for the decision-making (Meuleman 2019). The reliance on market-based instruments to set up key infrastructure providers may be too reliant on conditions reflecting ‘business-as-usual’, and therefore, limits their capability to provide resources during crisis periods (Entwistle et al., 2007). Moreover, the levels of fragmentation present within expanded decision-making arenas may result in

confrontations between a variety of perspectives – with professionals of varying backgrounds, where compromise may be difficult to reach (Bode and Firbank 2009). Providing stakeholders more autonomy for individual *ad hoc* decisions and interpretation to adjust the tools to fit the context may result in issues of accountability with actors exposing themselves towards risks (Capano and Toth 2023).

When instruments rely on varying logics, the tensions between them are likely to develop. The underlying challenges are strongly affected by the fundamental preference towards specific type of instruments over others (Howlett and Ramesh 2014). Stakeholders are used to specific instruments for cross-organisational and government-to-citizen interactions and a change of instruments can result in misinterpretations as well as conflicts with other stakeholders used to other type of instruments (Bode and Firbank 2009). This is due to the resources available as well as skills developed that affect the efficacy of instruments used. Here the advantages of a single ideal type may become an impediment for the other. For instance, the desired comprehensiveness and flexibility from network measures may run into conflict with already established hierarchical, representative or prescriptive instruments that establish the need for formalization (Entwistle et al., 2007). The extensive reliance on private partners for service provision can impede the skills of public actors to convene different type of actors together for an effective response (Howlett and Ramesh 2014). Furthermore, the increased reliance on contractual relations and outsourcing may result in the hollowing out of existing decision-making arenas, with the substantive roll shifting towards the contractual partners, relegating existing arenas from co-creators to advisors and creating considerable legitimacy issues (Wang 2023). Within decision-making, the national level and local level may have a disparity regarding the inclusion of different stakeholders and the perspectives they take (Ibid.). It may also be difficult to ensure solidarity of all partners, if there are partners with extrinsic motivations and partners with intrinsic or prosocial motivation involved.

Alongside the conflicts inherent in using configurations of ideal types, the crisis-specific conditions can also induce specific conflicts. The urgency, uncertainty and pressure from crisis provides considerable flexibility for public agencies at earlier stages of a crisis, with rally around the flag effect providing decision-makers leeway in devising a response to address the crisis, encouraging the use of command-and-control instruments over trust-based instruments (Greer et al. 2021). However, the inability to provide a symbol of a strong response can damage the legitimacy of the stakeholders. Over time, the growing awareness of the broader societal consequences may favour expanding the decision-making arenas as well as implement additional safeguards for the implementation process. As a result of the interplay between the different conditions, same configurations can be complementary in some contexts, conflicting in other contexts (Tenbenschel 2018). The inherent tensions with the use of different ideal type based instruments may develop over time and reach a breaking point during which the existing configuration is altered into a new configuration with a new balance of instruments used.

6. Conclusion

Although the existing literature has started to delve into the mixing and matching of different ideal types, it has yet to establish itself prominently. The focus within the literature on hybridity has continued to remain focused on the contrasts and compatibilities between the different ideal types, which remain quite vague, with limited insight into the possible combinations, as the normative responses tend to remain mono-paradigmatic. Furthermore, whilst hybridity has been slowly making progress in the different sub-strands of literature surrounding crisis responses, the configurations have been connected to specific contexts rather than looking at the possible variations of combining ideal types. This has resulted in the current insights remaining relatively simplified constructs with limited applicability. The emphasis on singular optimal responses in specific contexts limits the ability to comprehend the different possible configurations and therefore does not make optimal use of the potential of the concept of hybridity. Whilst a crisis response may be theoretically optimal in specific stages with the speed that hierarchical, representative and prescriptive instruments provide, and at other stages with the acceptance and inclusiveness that network, participative and reflexive instruments provide, the limitations from the patchwork of past reforms that public administrations have gone through render these configurations often unfeasible and undesirable.

The challenges within the ideal types, between the ideal types, between ideal type typologies and from the crisis-specific context result in consistent stress-tests for the hybrid configurations raising questions on how robustness as introduced in WP2 appears for hybridity. Whilst the optimal responses on specific contexts provide insights on the advantages and trade-offs, the optimal response in its static form remains inflexible to respond to the challenges brought about by crises and turbulence. Rather than searching for a single optimal response to address the crisis situations, robustness is highlighted in the capability to shift from one configuration to another. This includes the selection and choice of alternative instruments adhering to different ideal types that fit the specific context and meet the expectations of stakeholders. This is consistent also with the findings of WP5, which highlights the importance in the exchange of knowledge from a multitude of perspectives and coordinating through the existing epistemological hierarchy. The flexibility towards shifting from one configuration to another is dependent on the openness towards alternatives that is achieved through a learning process that necessitates overcoming the dominance of specific perspectives.

The theoretical lens of hybridity provides novel insights into how crisis responses take place. This paper has created an overview on the relevance of hybridity within single ideal type typologies and certain forms between ideal type typologies. It also provided preliminary findings regarding the trade-offs and advantages of the different configurations. Most importantly, the paper has offered an analytical lens for the study hybridity in future research.

Instead of utilizing a static logic of describing optimal configurations within specific contexts, the dynamic nature of hybridity should be the focal point. Rather than fitting optimal responses towards specific contexts, analysing the adaptability through the variations of configurations provides a toolset for comprehending robustness. Future empirical analyses within WP4 will improve our understanding on the creation of robustness for public administrations to bounce back and capitalize on short-term shocks and long-term instability. Only through further analysis will it be possible to construct a stronger understanding regarding the 'who', 'how' and 'what' in the crisis context.

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Annex 1. Examples of hybridity in literature

<i>Author</i>	<i>Concept</i>	<i>Definition</i>	<i>Description</i>
<i>Kooiman (2000)</i>	Modes of Governance	Social-political interactions	<p>Self-governance: the parts of the system are able to govern themselves in autonomy;</p> <p>Co-governance: the autonomous parts of the system interact in a multilevel setting with each other, although many of these relations are horizontal;</p> <p>Hierarchical governance: the autonomous parts partially give up their autonomy under certain conditions according to a top-down relationship.</p>
<i>Van Kersbergen and Van Waarden (2004)</i>	Governance Styles	Processes of decision-making and implementation with specific actor compositions	Nine prominent approaches for governance styles, with a vertical and horizontal approaches, networks and hierarchies, inclusion of different public, private and societal actors
<i>Jessop (2011)</i>	Metagovernance	Organising the conditions of governance through development of dynamic combinations of governance styles and their management	Rebalancing market, hierarchy and networks
<i>Brandesen and Karre (2011)</i>	Hybridity	Heterogeneous arrangements, characterized by mixtures of pure and incongruous origins, (ideal)types, cultures, coordination mechanisms, rationalities, or action logics.	<p>A triangle of different coordination mechanisms – state, community and market.</p> <p>Mixing the rationales of different coordination mechanisms to achieve quality public services.</p>
<i>Larsson (2017)</i>	Metagovernance	Creating, promoting and willingness to adjust instruments that enable the continuation of a system in different contexts (i.e. crisis management).	<p>Pragmatic view - finding and implementing the most appropriate governing structure (hierachy, network, market) or combination of different governing mechanisms in order to reach a specific policy goal.</p> <p>Network management view - facilitate, and manage multilateral policymaking, but consider the autonomy and perspective of the stakeholders involved.</p>
<i>Meuleman (2019)</i>	Metagovernance	coordinated decision-making and implementation through	Combinations between hierarchical, network and market governance adapted to meet specific contexts

		designing and managing sound combinations of ideal types to achieve the most suitable outcomes	
<i>Christensen, Lægreid and Rykkja (2016)</i>	Governance capacity	Coordination, regulation and implementation capacity which involves issues of hierarchy, networks and lead agency to deliver efficient and effective crisis management.	Centralization vs collaborative network
<i>Pierre and Peters, (2021); Christensen et al. (2022)</i>	Governance arrangements	Structures and processes by which regulatory instruments to cope with the pandemic were proposed, scrutinized, and enacted	(i) hierarchically structured command and control process vs. (ii) a network-based structure in which decisions are made by consensus
<i>(Richardson 2012)</i>	Modes of Governance		Centralization: command-and-control governance where the decision-making process centres on one specific point only. Decentralization: putting the control of crisis management in the hands of those closest to society. Collaborative crisis management (CCM), an arrangement where multiple stakeholders from different sectors and backgrounds work together to manage a crisis.
<i>(Richardson 2012)</i>	Policy Styles	the institutional arrangements within which policy deliberations take place and the actors and ideas present in such deliberations	the government's approach to problem-solving (anticipatory v. reactive) + state-society relations in terms of aiming to reach consensus or not.
<i>Howlett and Tosun (2019)</i>	Policy Styles		patterns of administrative arrangements, i.e., autonomy, aspirations and staffing. + state-society relations, compose the consensus seeking dimension, the degree of inclusiveness of social actors in policymaking and its level of formalization.
<i>Sørensen and Torfing (2019)</i>	Hybrid democracy	Combining together two distinct forms of democracy	Combining representative and participatory forms to enhance the strengths of the individual forms, limit their weaknesses and fundamental tensions and create contextual robustness